

Urban Planning and Spatial Transformation

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ABSTRACT:

Urban planning and spatial transformation is a future-oriented activity, which links “scientific and technical knowledge to actions in the public domain”. Planning as a general activity is the making of an orderly sequence of actions that will lead to the achievement of a stated goal or goals. Urban planning is just a sub-class of a general activity called planning; it is concerned with managing and controlling a particular system, the urban system. The field, in particular, focuses on the use of space, shaping the geographical layout of a city, zoning specific areas for development and deciding on the location of major public facilities like utilities and transportation corridors. The fields of urban planning involve the planning, design, operation, and management of infrastructure and resources. It incorporates a collection of spatial and non-spatial data regarding transportation, household, public services and life quality, population and activities for people. The human environment is concerned with change; therefore planning concepts must be dynamic, not static to cope with this transformation. The concept of an information society has been described by many scientists and futurologists the information society depending on five main criteria; these are: technological; economy; occupational; spatial; cultural. The technological criterion refers to the development of information and communication technology, and its effects on social development. The economy criterion refers to the development of new products that affect industrial structures. The occupational criterion refers to the development of new types of work places and occupational restructuring. The spatial criterion refers to the development of different types of networks and their effects on the organization of time and space. The cultural criterion refers to the rapid increase in information in social circulation.

KEYWORDS:

Urban Planning, Development, Spatial Transformation, Principles.

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INTRODUCTION

The spatial planning characteristics defined at the conference were democratic, comprehensive, functional and long-term-oriented. Prospects of development and of spatial planning in maritime. In almost 30 years, the interpretation of spatial planning has revolved almost at the same characteristics: participation or inclusion (democratic), coordination (comprehensive), common interests or cultures, etc. Sustainable. In recent decades, new additions and changes have been made to Spatial Planning approaches to maintain the characteristics initiated at the 1983 conference. In order to address various kinds of situations such as radical changes in politics, economy, transformation etc., an ideal spatial planning system always reinvents itself. Innovation is important to continually allowing spatial planning practices to adapt as per the conditions in institutional spatial planning settings. Spatial planning innovation can be derived from advances in technological instruments, the joint effort of formal and informal institutions with a common objective, and the ability of formal and informal institutions to adapt to project-based development. "The task of the planning enterprise is to critically interrogate the governance practices that currently exist and to help governance communities concerned with place qualities to develop different approaches where these are seen to be failing. This involves attention to both policy and practices; to what already exists, what is emerging and what might possibly emerge in a specific context. Local Government as Best Placed to Achieve Spatial Transformation According to the Constitution and the White Paper on Local Government, local government's developmental duty is to "work with residents and groups within communities to identify sustainable solutions to address their social, economic, and material needs and to improve the quality of their lives". The expectation of local government is to be the most redistributive and transformative realm of government closest to the people. However, the local government faces difficulties in carrying out its development mandate since it is expected to achieve more with less financial and personnel resources while also developing and maintaining the capacity and skills necessary for transformative delivery, the 'idea that local government is best placed to serve inhabitants and drive transformation is not challenged.' However, it is crucial to emphasise that local government's ability to achieve national policy objectives is a source of concern due to various problems. Institutional reform, corruption,

political involvement, inadequate financial management, and a lack of capacity development are among the problems

OBJECTIVES OF THE PAPER

1. To study the development of urban planning practice
2. To know the spatial transformation
3. To study the principles of spatial transformation

METHODOLOGY

The secondary data are drawn classified from the monthly journals, published Magazines, Handouts, company Website Annual reports, internet websites on urban planning and spatial transformation and apart from this, different edition of daily newspapers, were also used for the purpose of collection the information.

DEVELOPMENT OF URBAN PLANNING PRACTICE

1. Shift from government towards governance

Traditionally, a strong hierarchical approach was assumed in spatial planning, in which the central government was responsible for long-term strategic decisions. Nowadays, self-organizing, complex, and dynamic inter-organizational networks are characteristics of the social political world. Today it is argued that spatial developments are shaped through the interaction of many different stakeholders. Also there is a growing recognition of interdependence between stakeholders as a basic governing principle in a continuous process of negotiating. The shift from government to governance emphasizes social interaction, a system in which collaboration with a range of stakeholders is the central concern. This concept is related to the idea of interactive planning. The shift implies a development of governing styles that entails a broad network of public, semi-public and private stakeholders. Governance seeks to enhance collective goals and is primarily concerned with the coordination and fusion of public and private resources.

2. Shift from sector specific planning towards integrated

Planning A shift from sector planning towards integrated planning could also be signalized in the planning practice. For centuries, the various spatial functions have been divided between several planning sectors, each focused on its own specific part of planning. Urban planning, rural planning, transportation planning, electricity, and water management have

remained largely separate sectors. Traditionally, urban planning aimed at the coordination of real estate functions. Until recently, water and environmental functions were barely considered.

3. Shift from urban planning product to urban planning process

Traditionally, urban planning (rational planning) had a strong focus on physical results. The emphasis of a rational comprehensive planning concept is on the development of an extensive plan that gives a description of the land use plan showing the desired end-solution. The key criticism of rational comprehensive planning is its over-reliance on the 'objective possibilities' to prescribe the future of an area. A second criticism on rational comprehensive planning was the inflexibility of the master plans. It took years to develop a master plan, while in the meantime the context changed. Master plans were not flexible enough to take new constructions and other developments into account, which implied that newly developed master plans were already outdated before they were implemented.

4. Shift from 2D urban planning towards 3D visualization

Under the current development planning system, two-dimensional site plans are commonly used to communicate planning and design information. While the uses of two-dimensional site plans are convenient and adaptable for professionals, they are often unsuitable for the layperson. By nature, we live in a three-dimensional world, visualizing and understanding spatial relationships in three dimensions. The communication of planning and design information in two-dimensional form can often lead to a misinterpretation of design and planning issues. A majority of people find it hard to understand and read two-dimensional maps. To supplement two-dimensional site plans, developers and local authorities often use artist impressions. These impressions are not, however, suited to convey the detail of planning and design issues.

SPATIAL TRANSFORMATION

Transformation can be seen as 'a spatially defined, socially embedded process; an interrelated series of materially driven practices, whereby the form, substance and overall dimensions of urban space are purposefully changed to reflect the principles of a more equitable social order'. Transformation, as Williams defined it more than a decade ago, is a "programmatically, plan-oriented, project directed effort to change unequal access. A multi-dimensional open-ended, fluid process of

change organically linked to the past, present, and future. It is becoming increasingly clear that 'spatial transformation' is essential to redress historical injustices. However, it is a concept with a lot of ambiguous interpretations. The word has been broadly defined in public policy, academic research, and popular writing to describe to "significant urban change or reorganization". Instead of attempting fundamental change, spatial transformation is also used interchangeably with the idea of urban restructuring, which can refer to efforts that restructure while keeping the underlying power structures in order to minimize disruption and turbulence. The public's perception of the government's involvement in shaping and developing cities and towns in South Africa has shifted in the last two years. Institutional reforms, capacity building, and the reconfiguration of power and influence are all integrally tied to the transformation of space. Fundamentally, the experience of urban residents can be related to the transformation of space. Residents of an inclusive, productive, sustainable, and well-governed city enjoy a high quality of life, benefiting from what the city has to offer while also contributing to its creation and molding. It is critical to recognize that certain pathologies emerge in the city when people are unable to determine, influence, and ultimately access opportunities.

PRINCIPLES OF SPATIAL TRANSFORMATION

Scholars have noted that South African cities have different histories, configurations and challenges. Therefore, the vision of a spatially transformed city needs to allow for different variations. Therefore, in a South African cities' perspective, there cannot not be a descriptive or a specific intervention, but rather an emphasis on a set of principles that can inform the decisions made to ensure that they are in line with the spatial transformation goals and objectives. At a fundamental level, proposed that meaningful transformation requires:

1. Change in power imbalances;
2. The restructuring of space to achieve increased efficiency, spatial justice and equity;
3. Institutional transformation;
4. Developing organizational and managerial capacity; and
5. a focused vision and plan to achieve a transformative goal.

6. Tackles the inherited apartheid spatial legacy of exclusion, distorted growth patterns and inefficiencies;
7. Unlocks developmental potential through targeted investment in economic and social infrastructure;
8. Guides and informs investments in infrastructure that supports long-term inclusive growth;
9. Manages economic and demographic shifts to achieve productivity through agglomeration; and
10. Facilitates coordination between government and various actors which shapes and informs spatial development.

CONCLUSION

The development of urban societies will, according to the earlier discussion, consist of very different development prospects. The human dimension and the environment at a context are important elements, to be considered in the new urban planning theory. So there is an immense need for new urban planning theories. Therefore, the interplay in the creation of urban theories with spatial theories is relevant and important. New spatial and urban theories would form a reliable foundation to the development of new planning methods and models. Since life becoming more complex, universal solutions will not work. Therefore, there is a need for the creation of new planning methods and approaches for different types of planning tasks. Such approaches would offer a new way of dealing with the development of new types of communities. Urban planners have responded to develop urban planning by developing supportive tools, such as network-based geographic information system (GIS) as well as online public participation programs and other types of networking. These technologies have the capacity to automate data handling, reduce planning time, and increase the opportunities for public participation. To incorporate a new aspect into the old planning system is not an easy task. Planners have moved beyond drawing land-use plans to examining the evolution of urban activities, to monitor and analyze urban societal and environmental problems.

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